

STRUGGLE FOR WOMEN'S RIGHTS IN IRANIAN SOCIETY: FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT

(EARLY XX-XXI CENTURIES)

Doi: 10.54952/DHR.2022.61.25.024

Sanobar SHADMANOVA,
Doctor of historical sciences,
proff. Tashkent State University
of Oriental Studies

Temur QOCHQOROV,
2nd year Masters Degree in
Tashkent State University
of Oriental Studies

Abstract. In Iranian society, the formation, development, and achievements of women in the struggle for their rights in the early 20th and 21st centuries are discussed. It also discusses the negative and positive consequences of this social struggle, as well as the obstacles and opportunities of women that exist in Iran.

Key words: Women's Movement, Reza Shah Pahlavi, White Revolution, Islamic Revolution, discrimination, chodra, Kashf-e hijab.

Аннотация. Мақолада Эронда XX асрнинг охири – XXI асрнинг бошларида аёлларнинг ўз ҳақ-ҳуқуқлари учун кураши, унинг шаклланиши, ривожланиши ва натижалари ҳақида сўз боради. Шунингдек, мақолада бу ижтимоий курашнинг салбий ва ижобий оқибатлари, мавжуд муаммолар ва имкониятлар ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: Аёллар ҳаракати, Ризо Шоҳ Паҳлавий, Оқ инқилоб, Ислом инқилоби, дискриминация, чодра, Кашф-е ҳижоб.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются процессы становления, развития и достижения движения женщин Ирана в борьбе за свои права в конце XX – начале XXI вв.

Ключевые слова: Иран, женское движение, Реза Шах Пехлеви, Белая революция, Исламская революция, дискриминация, чадра, Кашф-э хиджаб.

Among the values promoted by popular culture today, sexual desire is much higher than maternal happiness, and the phrase “liberating a woman¹” is, in their view, a renunciation of her traditional duties as wife, mother, and housewife. No matter where you look at the moment – whether it’s women’s magazines, TV series, erotic novels or TV shows - you will see that women’s independence, success at work and sexual orientation are openly promoted².

– How did this happen in Iranian society?

Iran is based on a social movement for women’s rights. In Iran, women’s rights have changed with the way the country is governed, and women’s attitudes toward freedom and the right to self-determination have changed frequently³. With the rise of each government, a number of mandates on women’s rights have affected a wide range of issues, from suffrage to dress code⁴. The movement first emerged in Iran after the 1910 constitutional revolution, with the first women’s magazine published by women this year as a practical manifestation of the movement. The movement lasted until 1933, when the last women’s union was disbanded by the government of Reza Shah Pahlavi. This movement intensified again after the Iranian revolution (1979).

In 1962-1978, the Iranian Women’s Movement gained privileges such as the right to vote for women (part of the 1963 White Revolution of Muhammad Reza Shah). Also for women:

- allowed to participate in government agencies;
- In 1975, the Family Protection Act reduced new rights for women, including the right to large-scale divorce and women’s imprisonment, as well as polygamy⁵.

Women’s rights have been restricted in Iran since the Islamic Revolution. After the 1979 revolution, a number of laws were passed, such as the introduction of women’s mandatory headscarves and public dress codes. In November 2016, about 6 percent of Iran’s parliamentarians were women, compared to the overall average of 23 percent.

In Iran, the Women’s Rights Movement continues to influence reforms, with many efforts being made to end discrimination against women in particular.

The Iranian constitutional revolution took place between 1905 and 1911. The first attempts at women’s rights (more precisely, a lack of rights) that led to the emergence of society and magazines of women. The low status of women and the covert activities of many of their organizations and societies have somewhat limited the amount of information available in this regard. At that time, women’s writing, mainly through newspapers and periodicals, was one of the most valuable sources of information about the movement⁶.

In addition, Iranian women were aware of and inspired by women’s conditions and educational opportunities elsewhere.

A group of active women learned that education is essential for their goals. The main issue they later put forward is that educating women is important, that is, educating the next generation, which is important for the future of the country. In the early twentieth century, Christian missionaries established the first school for girls. Later, Haji Mirza Hasan Roshdie and Bibi Khanum Astarabadi also established schools for girls, but both soon closed⁷. Eventually, in 1918, after many years of private and unregulated schools, the government allocated funds to establish ten primary

¹ From the time the women’s movement was founded, its foundation was the unequal riots between men and women. Through political and social conflicts, attempts were made to close the gap on women’s equality. Throughout history, the role between men and women has been one of patriarchal societies, based on the law of nature, which has led to women being considered inferior to men. The feminist movement represents a series of social movements and political campaigns to carry out reforms on women’s issues due to inequality between men and women. The priorities of the movement have been expanding since the beginning of the early nineteenth century and vary between nations and communities.

² “First Wave Feminism”, *The Routledge Companion to Feminism and Post feminism*, Routledge, pp. 26–35, 23 November 2004, doi:10.4324/9780203 011 010-10, ISBN 978-0-203-01101-0, retrieved 10 July 2021.

³ Osanloo, Arzoo (2009). *The Politics of Women’s Rights in Iran*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. p. 20. ISBN 978-1-4008-3316-0. JSTOR.

⁴ Camara, Andrea (April 22, 2018). “Women’s Rights in Iran during the Years of Shah, Ayatollah Khomeini, and Khamenei”. Stars: 5–60.

⁵ “Gender Inequality and Discrimination: The Case of Iranian Women”. Iran Human Rights Documentation Center. March 5, 2013. Retrieved December 12, 2019.

⁶ Afary, Janet (1996). *The Iranian Constitutional Revolution (ICR), 1906–1911: Grassroots democracy, social democracy, and the origins of feminism*. Columbia University Press, New York ISBN 9780231103510.

⁷ *History of Medicine in Iran*. Archived from the original on July 2, 2009. Retrieved November 5, 2006.

schools for girls and a teacher training college. From 1914 to 1925, the subject of women's publications expanded, in which, in addition to discussing education, articles and reports on topics such as minors and non-economic and social powers began to be published.

In 1906, despite parliament rejecting their request, the women formed several organizations, including the Women's Freedom Society, which held secret meetings until they were identified by the government and attacked.

In 1922, Alexander the Great founded the Patriotic Women's Organization. The organization was persecuted by the government, its leader was arrested and his house was set on fire. Another activist, Zandokht Sherozi, founded the Women's Revolutionary Association. At this early stage of the women's movement, the women involved were the daughters, sisters, and wives of prominent constitutionalists. Typically, they were from educated middle-class families. The low status of women and the covert activities of many of their organizations and societies have limited the amount of information available.

In 1932, the Second Congress of Oriental Women was organized in Tehran, and Iranian women activists met with activists from Lebanon, Egypt, India, and Iraq. In 1936, Reza Shah Pahlavi forced women to cover their faces in a campaign called *Kashf-e hijab* - a highly controversial policy that allowed women to stay at home rather than be stripped of their veils and harassed by the police for not removing their veils, led to turning points in some areas of society.

The birth of many women's rights organizations began in Iran in the 1950s, including *Rah-e Nou* (The New Way), founded in 1955 by Mehrangiz Dovlatshahi, and the Women's League in Support of the Declaration of Human Rights by Safieh Firuz in 1956. Also in 1959, fifteen such organizations formed a federation in Iran called the Supreme Council of Women's Organizations. The Supreme Council decided to concentrate its efforts on women's right to vote.

Despite strong opposition from religious scholars, suffrage was included in the 1963 national referendum, which reflected the general support for a six-step

reform program called the White Revolution, which included women's right to vote and hold public office. In the elections, six women were elected to parliament (Majlis). In the late 1960s, women joined the diplomatic corps, the judiciary and the police, and the revolutionary service corps (education, health, etc.):

- In 1968, Farrokhro Parsa became the Minister of Education - she was the first woman to work in the state system;

- In 1969, the judiciary was opened for women and five women judges were appointed, including the future Nobel Laureate Shirin Ebadi.

- Women were elected to city, town and district councils.

In search of a way to achieve a more vital organizational structure for women's activities, a coalition of women's groups formed the Iranian Women's Organization in 1966.

The Iranian Women's Organization was a non-governmental primary organization working mainly through volunteers. Her goal was to encourage women to improve their education, to strive to ensure the economic independence of women, and at the same time to remain in the spirit of the cultural traditions of Islam and the nation. She worked through local branches and women's centers, which provided women with useful services for women - literacy classes, vocational training, counseling, sports and cultural events, and childcare in many jobs.

One of the important steps of the World Trade Organization was the adoption of the Family Protection Act in 1975. It gave women equal rights in marriage and divorce, expanded women's adoption rights, raised the minimum age of marriage to 18 for women and 20 for men, and practically banned polygamy⁸.

By 1978, almost 40% of girls aged 6 and over were literate; More than 12,000 women of the literacy corps taught in the villages; Thirty-three percent of university students were women, and more women than men took the medical school entrance exam. 333 women were elected to local councils, 22 women to parliament, and 2 to the Senate. There was one minister for women's affairs, 3 cabinet secretaries, one governor, an ambassador and five mayors⁹.

⁸ Sindawi, Khalid (2009). "Epilogue". *Temporary Marriage in Sunni and Shi'ite Islam: A Comparative Study*. Temporary Marriage in Sunni and Shiite Islam. Germany: Harrassowitz Verlag. pp. 119–122. ISBN 978-3-447-19154-8. JSTORj.ctvbqs3qn. 4.

⁹ Harrison, Francis (September 19, 2006). "Women graduates challenge Iran". Archived from the original on September 24, 2008. Retrieved September 21, 2008.

In the late 1970s, Iran established itself as a leading country for women's rights among developing countries, offering ideas and funding for the UN Regional Center for Regional Research and Development for Asia and the Pacific and the International Center for Women's Studies.

After the Iranian revolution in February 1979, the status of women changed radically. The large participation of women in the 1978-79 revolution was partly the result of the mobilization efforts of the women's organization in previous decades. Women marched in support of a free and equal government. Over time, some of the rights acquired by women during the King's reign were completely abolished, such as the forced hijab, especially the wearing of the headscarf. Shortly after the revolution, there were rumors of plans to force the hijab and abolish some women's rights protected by the Family Protection Act, which was declared "anti-Islamic." The rumors were denied by some government officials and many women refused to accept it. Soon, the rumors came true.

The new family law was repealed and the veil was forced to close. Farrokhro Parsa, the first woman to serve in the Iranian cabinet, was executed. Protests took place. The demonstrations are not aimed at expanding women's rights in Iran, but simply to preserve what they have earned. There were three main team attempts to express concerns:

- A five-day demonstration that began on March 8, 1979;
- December 1979 Women's Unity Conference;
- Demonstrations after Ayatollah Khomeini's decree to abolish any sign or practice reminiscent of the Shah's rule. The result of this decree was a mandatory hijab.

These collective efforts, as well as smaller ones, were not only confronted by Islamic conservatives, but were sometimes persecuted by left and right political groups. Indeed, most leftist groups did not have a clear vision or plan to protect women's rights. It has been argued that the status of women would

be automatically improved by building a socialist (communist) society.

Aspects of Islamic law concerning women can be seen in Articles 20 and 21 of the 1979 constitution, and two views of Islamic law are currently unpopular among women's rights activists: stoning and polygamy.

At the beginning of the Islamic Revolution, some of the leaders of women's rights were discredited. For the first time since the revolution, in 1997, several women managed to enter the stadium to watch a football game¹⁰. Women's legal counsel was introduced in special family courts.

One Million Signatures Significant Campaign to Abolish Discriminatory Laws, Another campaign launched in 2006 to collect one million signatures¹¹ to support discriminatory laws against women and family law reform in Iran, to ask parliament to revise and reform discriminatory laws – They always demanded to "stop stoning¹²".

According to statistics, the level of mobilization and awareness among women in Iran is remarkable. The women's rights movement is very active and organized. The movement also differs from other countries in that it uses information and communication technologies very wisely.

However, the active participation of many women in the revolution helped to awaken the political potential of women, and middle-class women acted to assert their rights. There has also been sharp opposition to policies banning polygamy, temporary marriages¹³, free divorces for men, and child custody. The growing trend of women began to interpret Islam as gender-equitable as more women entered the public and the rule of speech was curtailed. Increased activism and transparency have led to some legal remedies for women's struggles, such as restricting the husband's right to prevent his wife from being employed and introducing a new marriage contract that gives women the right to divorce¹⁴. Judges later became more sympathetic to women's issues, and when some

¹⁰ "It's Too Early To Cheer the So-Called End of Iran's Notorious Ban on Women in sports stadiums". Human Rights Watch. November 30, 2018. Archived from the original on February 24, 2019. Retrieved December 18, 2018.

¹¹ Burki, Shireen (2006). Islamic politics, human rights and women's claims for equality in Iran. *Third World Quarterly*. pp. 177–180.

¹² Ayatollah Challenges Parliament as It Mulls Equal Blood Money For Women". *radiofarda*. Retrieved March 8, 2019.

¹³ Sindawi, Khalid (2009). "Epilogue". *Temporary Marriage in Sunni and Shi'ite Islam: A Comparative Study*. Temporary Marriage in Sunni and Shi'ite Islam. Germany: Harrassowitz Verlag. pp. 119–122. ISBN 978-3-447-19154-8. JSTORj.ctvbqs3qn. 4.

¹⁴ "Gender Inequality and Discrimination: The Case of Iranian Women". Iran Human Rights Documentation Center. March 5, 2013. Retrieved December 12, 2019.

reforms were not implemented through the legislative process, the government tried to mitigate some of the injustices and instructed the courts on how to do so.

Newspapers, magazines, and organizations that support women's rights and freedoms have also been active in Iran. One such magazine is Zanan, a monthly women's magazine founded in 1992 in Iran. It was the only magazine of Persian women in the country. The magazine ceased publication in 2008, but was republished on May 29, 2014. In September 2014, its founder and editor, Shahla Sherkat, promoted non-Islamic and "outdated" views in the Iranian Press Court (part of the Islamic Revolutionary Court), and in April 2015, the magazine was suspended again. Zanan magazine focused on the problems of Iranian women from an Islamic perspective, with the intention of protecting and supporting their rights. The articles cover controversial issues ranging from domestic violence to plastic surgery. It emphasized that gender equality was Islamic and that religious literature had been misread and misappropriated by misogynists. Zanan editor Mehngiz Kar, Shahla Lahiji and Shahla Sherkat debated women's rights and called for reforms. The leadership did not respond to this, but for the first time since the revolution did not stop the social movement from taking practical action.

My Secret Freedom is an online movement that was started in 2014 by Alinajot, an active journalist born in the UK, Iran. The move began with the My Stealthy Freedom Facebook page, where Iranian women post their photos anonymously, and by the end of 2016, Facebook had surpassed 1 million likes. The initiative was widely publicized internationally and nationally, with the re-election of Iranian President Hassan Rouhani as a hope for his election

to repeal a mandatory hijab law that had never been repealed before. To that end, Alinajot launched White Wednesday, where women wore white veils on Wednesday to protest the law (men wear white ribbons on their wrists in unison). But these efforts, as always, ended in failure.

There are currently master's degree programs in women's studies at Allameh Tabatabayi University, Tarbiat Modares University, Alzahra University and Tehran University in Iran, as well as three sub-majors: women and family, women's history and women's rights in Islam. These programs train specialists to address some of the damage caused by the prevalence of negative attitudes toward women in Iran for hundreds of years, as well as socio-humanitarian and other challenges. It is likely that in the future, graduates of women's training programs will offer views on gender equality.

Incumbent President Ibrahim Raisi has won an election campaign with a political program aimed at expanding women's participation in government. The current head of government in the Islamic Republic of Iran predicts that decisions will be made not only by the people, but also by the international community, which will make a huge political turn. Of course, these decisions do not by pass women's rights.

In conclusion, the struggle for women's rights in Iran has been going on for more than a century. In Iranian society, many women's rights to this process have been restricted by the constitution since the late 1970s (after the 1979 Islamic Revolution), but they are still fighting harder for their freedoms. From the current head of government, women, who are one of the key links in society, are hoping to reach new heights.

